

State of investment in the equitable and digital transformation of health systems in Egypt

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Summary

Digital transformation provides Egypt a special opportunity to shift in many economic areas including health, whereas generating possibilities for persons and businesses and influencing comprehensive progress and economic expansion. If correctly implemented, digital transformation might be a good counterbalance resulting in both digital access and much critically, digital equity. Despite that digital transformation could bring a critical economic impact, it must be backed-up by the needed technological infrastructure, human resources, and the suitable laws, among other enablers to make digital transformation a stage for equity but not disparities. This report highlights the present status of Egypt's digital maturity, the adoption of information and communication technology (ICT) by the health sector, and the achievements and the likely challenges for digital transformation in health.

Health Financing System in Egypt

Egypt continues to implement significant public financial reforms, which contribute to fiscal consolidation. Inflation, on the other hand, has been high in recent years. To mitigate the impact of inflation on living conditions, the Central Bank tightened monetary policy and the government increased social protection spending. GDP was \$404.14 billion in 2021, with a per capita GDP of \$3876.4 (World Bank, 2021a, 2021b). General government spending totalled US\$ 32.1 billion, accounting for 7.9% of GDP (World Bank, 2021c, 2021d). The poverty rate at the national poverty line increased from 19.6% in 2004 to 29.7% in 2019 (State Information Service, 2021; World Health Organization. Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean, 2019).

Egypt's health-care system is complex, with numerous public and private financing arrangements. The system is disjointed, with numerous public entities involved in management, financing, and care delivery. Several finance agencies are currently available in both the public and private sectors. The Ministry of Health and Population receives funds from the Ministry of Finance to operate hospitals and primary health care facilities throughout the country's 27 governorates. There are several financially autonomous government-owned organizations, the largest of which is the Health Insurance Organization, which has the status of a para-statal entity. Furthermore, a number of ministries, including the Ministries of Defence,

Interior, and Higher Education, act as public financing agents by pooling public funds and covering various groups of the population. Numerous private insurance companies, funds managed by unions and professional organizations, and funds managed by non-profit organizations are examples of private sector financing agents. Finally, households serve as the primary financing agent, with out-of-pocket payments accounting for a sizable portion of current health expenditure (World Health Organization. Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean, 2019).

Egypt's ability to raise public revenue is primarily determined by the country's economic situation, which influences the country's ability to levy taxes. Although current health expenditures as a share of GDP were 5% in 2019, households remain the single largest source of financing, accounting for roughly 71% of current health expenditure. In addition to contributions from those insured, employers, loans and grants, and general government payments on behalf of those unable to pay for health services. Egypt has a low level of risk sharing, with domestic general government health expenditure accounting for 28% of current health expenditure in 2019. Because of the Ministry of Health and Population's limited financial capacity, many people are unable to access services. Out-of-pocket payments were 63 % of current health expenditure in 2019, indicating that many people in the country are at risk of financial ruin and impoverishment (World Health Organization. Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean, 2019; World Health Organization (WHO), 2019). Annex 1 demonstrates Health Expenditures in Egypt in 2019.

Landscape in relation to digital maturity and key players

Based on the latest Global Competitiveness report, Egypt was classified as the 82nd out of 141 states and was one of the handful states possessed growing advances in comparison to earlier times, hence highlighting several accomplishments in the managerial and economic areas whereas displaying the state's capacity to fight economically (Schwab & Zahidi, 2020). Based on the latest World Economic Outlook update in July 2021, Egypt's economy grew into 3.6 % in 2020 down from the 5.6% in 2019 prior to the COVID-19 pandemic strike, with economic projected growth of 2.8% in the fiscal year 2021 and 5.2% in the fiscal year 2022 (International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2021).

An investigation on the effect of ICTs on Micro, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (MSMEs) in Egypt included 105 businesses from 37 various sectors, covering health, among others. They found that there was an obvious progressive but quite delayed shift in MSMEs' environment from avoiding risk to driving the deployment of ICT (S. Kamel, 2016).

A certain impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is the higher spending and attention to health services, especially health-tech and telehealth. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare services has accelerated efforts in Egypt to improve the digital capabilities of future healthcare

professionals. Egypt perhaps spends about ten billion dollars over new beds for health facilities, thus the space for development is certainly present (Youssef et al., 2020). Investments in ventures exceptionally expanded in 2021, with fintech ranked the first. Regarding budgeting, health, ranked the fourth, recorded a rise of 20 % (with 12 deals) in deployed funds than that of 2020 (MAGNITT, 2022).

The state of national digital health strategies

Egypt is investing in digital transformation

Egypt's Reform 2.0 strategy covers five major pillars including fostering ICT expansion, with healthcare getting a focus for government budgeting (Enterprise, 2021). Egypt released the Universal Health insurance Law 2 in 2018, with a digital transformation plan, originally started in Port Said, Luxor, and Ismailia, to establish a database labelling patients by the national ID number and enabling physicians and cases to exchange examination findings, linking physicians and pharmacies to accessible drugs, feasible guidance and referrals (Abdel-Hafez, 2020).

The worldwide digital health market has expected growth to about 341.17 billion dollars in 2028 utilizing wide Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions (Statistics Market Research Consulting, 2022). This could be linked to Egypt's target of having 7.7 % of its GDP (42.7 billion dollars) coming through AI by 2030 according to the state's national AI strategy that targets merging technology solutions in various areas, involving health (MCIT, 2021).

The Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT) has led many initiatives in partnership with other Ministries and the private sector to foster digital transformation (Annex 2) and release the Sustainable Development Goals involving seven main pillars covering e-Health, and ICT, among others (S. H. Kamel & Rizk, 2019). The MCIT is cooperating with the Ministry of Health (MOH) in digital transformation throughout systems and has been driving universal healthcare and interdisciplinary partnerships. For example, the cooperation with Vodafone, the English telecommunication operator, in a deal of 100 million Euro to establish the modern health insurance IT system. Adopting the style of the UK National Health Services (NHS), It would provide universal health for Egypt citizens. Vodafone operates through DXC Technology, an enterprise supplying IT infrastructure services over the NHS supply chain, to build a stage for digital health services for initiating the universal health insurance project in Egypt (Department for International Trade & The Rt Hon Liam Fox MP, 2019). Vodafone would fully digitalize hospitals starting with information management systems, leveraging radiology and laboratory systems, and fiscal management, among others. Yet, systems are in the adoption phase and the project is ongoing, with an expected accomplishment in the following couple of years (Anderson et al., 2021).

The prospect for the health industry is rather optimistic. The COVID-19 pandemic is foreseen to grow financing, mainly by external sponsors, and the government has already revealed an early 63.5 million dollars as additional support for the healthcare after the COVID-19 pandemic strike. In 2020 the IMF granted a 1-year, 5.2 billion dollars Agreement to promote essential structural reforms, sustain healthcare expenses, and enhance financial transparency to encourage an enterprise-driven ecosystem that is instrumental to much broader, private-sector-guided development and employment opportunities (S. Kamel, 2021).

The Health industry is foreseen to expand critically and would witness a great leap in the near future for both health stakeholders and beneficiaries, and could be mirrored in the opened possibilities for modern ventures and MSMEs. The rising figure of health-tech ventures arrives in parallel with the more investments in the Egyptian health sector, in particular revealing schemes of adopting universal health coverage (UHC) by 2032 that is anticipated to promote more development. The UHC is an attempt to build more potentials for the innovative solutions of modern health ventures. Currently, there are over 100 ventures in Egypt fostering innovation in health and meeting the increasing needs (Youssef et al., 2020). Much of those healthcare entrepreneurs have adopted distant health and supported in fighting the COVID-19 pandemic.

Key developments and achievements

Today, the healthcare industry is using integral techniques to reach the entire society, such as Tele-awareness for the public, telehealth for the patients and e-learning for healthcare providers. Currently, many digital health initiatives are being adopted to guarantee the community can access health services with better reach, extent and quality, and savings in patients' cash and time with fiscal durability of healthcare coverage. For example the Universal Health Insurance scheme, the National Network for Public Health Treatment, the Clinical Laboratory Information Systems and several Mobile phone solutions for Health, which raise health awareness via short messaging service to support preventing and controlling the dissemination of chronic conditions', like diabetes, hypertension, among others (Dahroug, 2019). Moreover, digital transformation activities led to establishing a database of all diabetic patients in Egypt and allowed emphasizing health services for COVID-19 cases, particularly who had comorbidities (Abdel-Hafez, 2020).

COVID-19 fostered digital health

In rural areas of Egypt and notably in the era of COVID-19 pandemic, telehealth had a broader reach to promote health in comparison to traditional techniques. Besides, Health-tech and wellness are getting attention with stages reflecting modern entrepreneurial ventures, which

are changing the health sector and showing the abundance of possibilities that might be established for the private sector (Youssef et al., 2020). Hence, Egypt has initiated a chain of reforms to help modern ventures and expand private contribution in the health industry. Yet, the path to implementing EHR across the Egyptian healthcare system will be difficult and will require multiple trials over time (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The path to implementing EHR across the Egyptian healthcare system.

In Egypt, entrepreneurs are a game changer via unique digital health innovations in services like reserving appointments, searching for physicians, among other online healthcare services. In Egypt, e-health startups and SMEs are focusing on expanding the reach of medical services via the internet and providing patients with information to help them make informed medical decisions (Table 1).

Vezeeta is an online medical care scheduling service that provides a free medical search platform for end users by integrating information about medical practices and individual doctors' schedules in a central location. It also provides access to teleconsultations and physicians' home visits and online ordering of pharmaceuticals. Launched in 2012, Vezeeta links clients with 21,000 locally-authorized physicians in 41 medical specialities (Anderson et al., 2021). The Cairo-based startup has now expanded to cover 15% of the MENA population across 8 cities, with over 2,000,000 people using it each month.

Shezlong is a mental health platform that allows patients to virtually communicate with their therapist online, privately, and from any location. The web platform enables users to search a community of therapists, reserve a session from available dates, select an appropriate payment method, and communicate privately with the therapist online (Shezlong,

2022). **SuperMama** is an Arabic parenting service focused at Middle Eastern mothers. It offers various types of written and visual localized content to mothers in the region, ranging from getting pregnant to raising children, managing a home, and caring for her health and beauty, as well as online forums where mothers can share advice.

Through innovative tailored software solutions and streamlined operations, **Smart medicare Care** provides corporate clients with customized and discounted health care plans as well as access to over 400 health care providers (hospitals, clinics, etc.). Through a socially inclusive business model, it also aims to provide healthcare solutions for the underprivileged and uninsured classes. **D-Kimia** creates novel and cost-effective diagnostic solutions. The low-resource diagnostic solutions are quick, inexpensive, and easy to use, and provide the same level of specificity as the most advanced Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) and other amplification-based diagnostic techniques.

E-health startups / (SMEs)	Coverage	Monthly visits	Funding	Employees
Vezeeta	MENA region	Over 2M	\$63.5M	100-250
Shezlong		Over 11,000	\$716,000	1-10
SuperMama		Over 7M	Over \$17,000	11-50
Smart medicare Care	Egypt	1,119	\$1.2M	100-250
D-Kimia		-	\$500,000	1-10

Health 2.0 Egypt, a section of the Health 2.0 Conference related to the Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society, and an ecosystem of digital health pioneers in Egypt, aims at linking digital health stakeholders with the domestic and universal innovation society. Through sharing knowledge, it opened new job opportunities, supported start-ups finding customers and sponsors. Now it is networking more than 3,000 individuals in 5 governorates, and operating several innovations' incubators that mentored more than 20 domestic start-ups, whereas some of them found their way in the local digital health market in Egypt (Anderson et al., 2021).

For health ventures, the COVID-19 pandemic with its different problems broke up the state of affairs and enhanced healthcare. For instance, following the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, a creative app named 7keema offered home-based nursing care to over 2,500 cases, involving the institution of intensive care in several personal dwellings. The health-tech venture O7 Therapy took the advantage provided by the COVID-19 pandemic and employed a web-based stage connecting people having psychological problems such as depression and anxiety with authorized specialists. Further, the Cleopatra Hospitals Group started a telehealth stage to address patients diagnosed with mild to moderate COVID-19; showing the influence and outreach capacity of telehealth and the potential to narrow the gap in care quality among rural and urban regions and emphasizing the potential shift, which might impact the whole health industry and, accordingly, the economy (Raven, 2021). In the era of COVID-19 pandemic, novel apps were developed to assist in controlling the situation, like contact tracing to trace individuals in-contact with confirmed COVID-19 cases (Kende, 2020). A number of such apps are multinational, and the rest are accessible domestically.

Key challenges

Despite the late structural and economic reforms that have put Egypt in a somewhat better place in confronting the COVID-19 pandemic, the consequences of the COVID-19 have definitely impacted economic growth, emphasizing the previously present problems. For example, the little funds assigned to healthcare – although it is better than former periods– and the country debt-to-GDP ratio, which went up to 92.9 % - although the latest and critical pre-COVID-19 decline (International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2021).

The limited reach and poor quality of digital networks and digital literacy are challenging elements for later growth. For instance, in Egypt, some populations are either uncovered or under-covered by broad bandwidth, therefore, they might not afford to access the Internet; others are not digitally literate thus, they would not gain from digital transformation, involving telehealth, among other digital services. This variability resulted from different disparities in the community involving: accessibility to technology, health, and other general services. Besides, legislation could foster these disparities, like the Data Protection Law, which necessitates a large application toll-1,250 dollars - for individuals to practice their data rights (Wilkinson & Ooijevaar, 2020). Surprisingly, the public structure has exhibited a number of special obstacles to digital transformation, like the inclination of women to have a female physician, and the recurrent absence of formal documents coupled with the need to provide a suitable health service, among others (Abdel-Hafez, 2020).

Discussions

The government is leading digital transformation to improve healthcare, consolidate ICT infrastructure in the health sector, establish advanced networks for better communication and data collection, grow skills of both managerial and healthcare providers, narrow the healthcare gap in distant locations, and generate a multi-alliance enterprise paradigm to harness the climate for digital transformation. Egypt is investing in digital transformation to decrease costs and offer quality healthcare to citizens. Furthermore, The COVID-19 pandemic has hastened digital transformation with the higher adoption of distant monitoring, telehealth stages and AI-empowered apps and gadgets.

Following the COVID-19 pandemic strike, and all its different impacts on community and economy, a mind shift regarding technology acceptance, spread, and adoption in Egypt. After the speeding up in digital transformation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, Egypt has an extraordinary potential to advance the sector of ICT to turn into a hub for a digital economy, opening the door for businesses and influencing economic growth. Overall, Egypt should have better foundations for healthcare, guided by the government or the private sector.

The exponential growth of computing technologies, as well as long-term socio-demographic trends, will also drive healthcare change. AI could save cost through substituting diagnostics processes earlier done via healthcare workers and supporting healthcare facilities to make a good use of the existing human resources. In Egypt, healthcare facilities generate a great volume of health-related data, besides consumer-generated data. It is vital to promptly and effectively utilize these huge data sets by cloud-based solutions, for example, health records. Hence, merging cloud-based data systems involving medical history, diagnoses, therapeutics, and previous appointments would shift the healthcare industry and might be applied in modern data analytics and retrieved timely, resulting in less expenses with better access to various health services.

However, the potential of digital transformation, there are numerous unaddressed issues, involving: alleviating the encountered barriers since the COVID-19 pandemic and at the same time making a better future; conquering the already existing problems prior to the COVID-19 strike, involving, the social disparities within income classes, gender, age and distant and deprived sites, these disparities could clearly be aggravated by more speeding up of digital transformation, except a prompt and broad technique is adopted throughout the country; and the community acceptance of the ICT environment, not only through digitizing sectors, but also through heading to the digital economy.

Despite the fact that there has been obvious development, there is yet a great deal to achieve, thereby the community gains from digital

transformation in health that could modify the way of living and occupations in Egypt. Hence, strategies should guarantee various communities in different geographical spots, involving rural and deprived regions, have reasonable access to technological solutions, in addition to the potential to gain the required understanding and digital skills to embrace them.

Medical schools must be encouraged to raise their educational standards and adopt new educational approaches. The emphasis must be on integrating technology into medical practice, as well as developing leadership and communication skills. The importance of dealing with "big data" should be emphasized. Health professionals need to pursue further virtual identities to reach patients via modern innovations, while patients would have the chance to try various services on the run. Though, local services adjusted to the domestic environment are required and could be based on the present web-based health services to both tackle the COVID-19 pandemic, and address permanent healthcare challenges.

Moreover, the legal structure needs to follow up on the web-based services offering medical counselling or marketing drugs. Some healthcare providers are concerned about the quality, and the likelihood of expired or illicit products, among others. Thus, legitimate solutions are required to guarantee the adherence of these services with legislation and the liability to suitable monitoring procedures, however, with no more exhaustive terms.

Conclusion

Digital transformation provides generous potentials for Egypt, yet, overall innovation, and concretely ICT is unable to address all the issues or respond to all community and economy problems, which have grown over the years. Although digital transformation is able to impact the economy and allow much useful enterprise setting, it needs assistance through the essential comprehensive digital framework, proficient human resources, and the right legitimate, administrative, capital, management, didactic, protection, among other enablers. The speeding up of digital transformation portrays an advantageous point for the authority to influence many economic areas and trades involving health. Though, for reaching universal, enduring, and effective economic expansion, Egypt should adopt an integrated technique to establish an active and integral environment, which emphasizes on the touch and capability empowered by digital transformation.

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Appendix

Annex 1: Egypt Health Expenditure in 2019 (World Health Organization (WHO), 2019).		
NHA Indicators		Value
Current Health Expenditure (CHE) as % of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)		5
Current Health Expenditure (CHE) per Capita in US\$		150
Current Health Expenditure (CHE) per Capita in PPP		582
Domestic Health Expenditure (DOM) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		99
Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) as % Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		28
Domestic Private Health Expenditure (PVT-D) as % Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		71
Out-of-pocket (OOPS) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		63
Voluntary Prepayments as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		7
External Health Expenditure (EXT) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		1
Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) as % of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)		1

Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) as % General Government Expenditure (GGE)		5
Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) per Capita in US\$		42
Domestic General Government Health Expenditure (GGHE-D) per Capita in PPP Int\$		162
Domestic Private Health Expenditure (PVT-D) per Capita in US\$		107
Domestic Private Health Expenditure (PVT-D) per Capita in PPP Int\$		414
External Health Expenditure (EXT) per Capita in US\$		2
External Health Expenditure (EXT) per Capita in PPP Int\$		6
Compulsory Financing Arrangements (CFA) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		29
Government Financing Arrangements (GFA) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		22
Compulsory Health Insurance (CHI) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		6
Social Health Insurance (SHI) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		6
Voluntary Financing Arrangements (VFA) as % of Current Health Expenditure (CHE)		71
General Government Expenditure (GGE) as % of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)		28

Current health expenditure by revenues of health care financing schemes	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	5
Transfers from government domestic revenue (allocated to health purposes)	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	1
Internal transfers and grants	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	1
Other domestic revenues n.e.c.	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	3
Other revenues from households n.e.c.	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	3
Current health expenditure by financing schemes	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	5
Government schemes and compulsory contributory health care financing schemes	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	1
Government schemes	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	1
Household out-of-pocket payment	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	3
Gross Domestic Product	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	100
Final consumption expenditure of Households and profit institutions serving households	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	83
General government expenditure	% Gross domestic product (GDP)	28
Purchasing Power Parity (NCU per Int\$)		4

Exchange Rate (NCU per US\$)		17
Gross domestic product - Price index (2020 =100)		100
Population (in thousands)		100,388

Annex 2: Initiatives in e-health in collaboration with MICT.

Initiative	Category	Sub-category
Ongoing		
Alexandria University Hospitals Development	E-health	Automation
Comprehensive Development and Automation of Ain Shams Hospitals		
Comprehensive Health Insurance Information System		
Pilot Projects for Hospital Automation & Information System Units (Alexandria University hospital, Al-Azhar spacialized hospital, Ain Shams hospital, Abu El Reish hospital, Suez Insurance Hospital)		
National Network for Treatment at Expense of State (Citizen Health)		Automation/ Teleconsultation
Completed		
Arab-African Telemedicine Network Initiative	Telemedicine	Knowledge sharing

Egyptian Telemedicine Network (ETN)		Diagnostics	
TeleMedic@Egypt Project		Teleconsultation	
Pan Africa Project		Teleconsultation	
Saving children through teleconsultation in remote Egypt		/E-learning	
Women's Health Outreach Program		Diagnostics/ database	
Emergency Medical Service Call Center Ambulance Project	E-health	Automation	
National Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS) Project			
Regional Center for Women's Health in Alexandria			
National Diabetes and Endocrinology Institute Operation Automation			
Health Insurance Organization Laboratories Information Network			
National Cancer Registry Program			Database
Digital Medical Files (Family Health Units)			
Information Technology (IT) Health Master Plan			Strategy
National Healthcare Capacity Building Project			Upskilling